

**A COMPONENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATIVE
COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH IS PROFESSIONAL ENGINEERING
KNOWLEDGE**

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Anotation: This article about methods and tools of knowledge of a component of professional communicative competence in English is professional engineering knowledge. Summarizing some of the progress made in education reform over the past decade, scholars recognize the need for large-scale modernization to improve quality and accessibility to meet society's demands.

Key words: methods, a competent approach, pedagogical system, a contextual approach.

The principles of integration based on interdisciplinary connections and the fundamental principles of educational content remain effective and gain new adherents. The concept of integration is considered by researchers as an educational principle that provides interdisciplinary complexity, generalization, density of knowledge, methods and tools of knowledge. Integration allows for a fragmented study of the conflict between the multifaceted and systematic-integral nature of education with a global character of philosophical concepts and goals through the subject type of education.

According to A.A.Verbitsky, another distinguishing feature of modern education is that it combines education and upbringing in a single pedagogical process, where education plays the main role, and education is one of its elements. Another category of education - design is also promising: its leading principles are: design of life activities in the field of education by students themselves, obtaining knowledge and

information from any sources other than the teacher, education at the same time as the formation of worldview¹.

The positive aspects of the competent approach reflected in pedagogical theory and educational practice are described by Maletina, L. V systematizes. He stated²:

- a competent approach simplifies and clarifies the relationship between the boundaries of didactic conditions in the design of educational and management processes;

- epistemologically, it meaningfully, effectively and instrumentally connects the goal, content, process of the methodical components of the educational system, makes the goal and content of education more dynamic, directs it to respond to changes in the labor market and the demand for personnel;

- a competent approach moves almost all management activities and decisions to a qualitatively new instrumental level, makes the management decision-making mechanism itself instrumental;

- a competent approach includes a sufficiently strong motivational component of the educational process.

Summarizing some of the progress made in education reform over the past decade, scholars recognize the need for large-scale modernization to improve quality and accessibility to meet society's demands. Thus, noting that the introduction of a competent approach to the educational process in higher education institutions is being implemented slowly and with difficulty, A.A. Verbitsky applied it to all links of the pedagogical system: the values, goals and results of education and training, the pedagogical activity of the teacher, the educational activity of students, emphasizes that

¹ *Вербицкий, А. А.* Компетентностный подход и теория контекстного обучения: Материалы к четвертому заседанию методологического семинара 16 ноября 2004 г. [Текст] / А. А. Вербицкий. — М.: Исследовательский центр проблем качества подготовки специалистов, 2004. — 84 с.

² *Малетина, Л. В.* Обучение иноязычному монологическому говорению во взаимосвязи с информативным чтением в процессе профессиональной подготовки будущего инженера [Текст]: дис. ... канд. пед. наук: 13.00.08 / Л. В. Малетина. — Пермь, 2007. — 197 с.

the implementation of technological support and other components of the educational process requires inevitable changes³.

Adoption of the third generation state educational standards sets new theoretical and practical tasks for educational institutions. These tasks are based on the positions of the well-known scientists of our country - the team of developers of the concept of modern humanistic education. The circumstances defined by them are convincing, clear, promising:

- development of state standards, competent models of their graduates by higher education institutions. It is suggested that such models should be designed with some degree of invariance, taking into account the interests of employers and higher education institutions. The invariant model should reflect the unique characteristics of the educational process as a whole. It is focused on ensuring compatibility between the goal of graduates and the level of their graduation competence, being independent of specialization, that is, having the characteristics of universality;

- to ensure the transition from competent models to actual basic educational programs, understanding their project on the basis of competent models of their graduates. In this, according to the competent model of modern specialist training, the qualities of a person, a specialist and a researcher should be reflected in his integrated abilities.

- If the foundations of the pedagogical system are described by A.A. Verbitsky's theory and practice of contextual education, it will be possible to systematically integrate educational, scientific and educational processes. Contested education raises the question of the natural need for regional and federal funding, not only for the systematic integration of processes, but also for the effective social cooperation of authorities, business, regional partners and the university.

Assessment of the level of formation of competencies is a process of assessment based on the competent direction of the prospective graduate and its correlation with the normative competent direction.

³ Вербицкий, А. А. Компетентный подход и теория контекстного обучения: Материалы к четвертому заседанию методологического семинара 16 ноября 2004 г. [Текст] / А. А. Вербицкий. — М.: Исследовательский центр проблем качества подготовки специалистов, 2004. — 84 с.

When solving these tasks, the aspect of knowledge assessment is transferred to the assessment of competences, that is, what the student can do and can do, his ability to perform activities is focused on. Forms of assessment based on the demonstration of competencies mastered by students prevail (essays, portfolios, concrete assignment projects).

The matrix of coordination of competences, functions and tasks of professional activity is an important means and forms of measuring the level of formation of relevant competences. The methodological value of the matrices shows, on the one hand, what competencies appear when solving professional tasks, and on the other hand, what competencies are needed for solving professional tasks.

Specific methods of implementing a contextual approach in the educational process are offered by modeling specific contexts of the professional activity of a specialty.

In conclusion, by dividing the indicated cases, we tried to design the contextual suitability of the formation of foreign language communication competences of students of technical higher education institutions, which ensures the rapid readiness of the young specialist to participate in intercultural cooperation situations, we chose the theory of contextual education as the specific conceptual basis of this research.

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